

Parachor and Chemical Constitution. Part I. Structure of the Carbohydrates.

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According to the modern conception of the structure of sugars as established by the work of Haworth and his collaborators (Haworth, "Constitution of Sugars," 1929) these bodies are represented as having an oxygen ring, but nevertheless owing to the ready reducing properties of the sugars it is admitted that this structure is anything but stable. The object of the present paper is to find out which of the following two structures agrees with the parachor contribution of the sugar molecule.

Two monosaccharoses, glucose and fructose and two disaccharoses, sucrose and maltose were investigated. The surface tension was determined by the method of maximum bubble pressure; the apparatus employed was of the usual Sugden type. The determination of surface tension in the fused condition, except in the case of fructose, was found to be extremely difficult as the sugars rapidly become brown on prolonged heating. Hence the determinations were made very quickly.

The surface tension of maltose in the fused state cannot be determined as it decomposes immediately on fusion. To obviate this difficulty the penta-acetyl derivative of glucose and the octa-acetyl derivatives of sucrose and maltose were also examined as they are found to be more stable. The densities were determined by means of a U-shaped pycnometer. It will be seen from the results that the parachor contribution agrees very closely with the oxide ring structure

as proposed by Haworth and his collaborators. Thus it can be definitely said that in the fused state sugar molecules exist as ring compounds.

The density and surface tension were determined also in solution and the parachor calculated from the results obtained (cf. Ray, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 671). The solvents employed were water and pyridine, the only two liquids in which the sugars were found to be fairly soluble. It will be seen that in the aqueous solutions normal results were obtained in very dilute solutions. With increase of concentration, after a certain limit, the parachor was found to diminish. In pyridine the values were never normal. With decreasing concentration of the sugars, the parachor increases rapidly and approaches the normal value. By plotting x against P_x , a curve is obtained which was found to intersect the P_x axis at the required value.

A, B, C and D refer to maltose, sucrose, glucose and fructose respectively.

These results will be evident from the curves given above. In this connection it is to be noted that similar results were obtained by Hammick and Andrew (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 754) with some liquid mixtures but their results were found to increase with increasing concentration.

TABLE I.

Parachor in fused state.

Carbohydrates.	Temp.	Density.	Surface tension.	Found P.	Calculated.	
					$P_{\text{ring.}}$	$P_{\text{open.}}$
Fructose	100°	1.459	72.83	360.6	360.1	377.2
	130°	1.435	68.64	360.8	360.1	377.2
Glucose	170°	1.461	71.73	358.8	360.1	377.2
Sucrose	170°	1.429	62.20	672.0	668.4	...
Penta-acetyl-glucose	150°	1.141	25.96	771.5	779.1	796.2
Octa-acetyl-sucrose	78°	1.257	36.91	1331	1339	...
Octa-acetyl-maltose	170°	1.185	30.04	1399	1336	...

In Table II, x is the molar fraction of the solute, M_m the mean molecular weight of the solution, P_m the mean parachor and P_x the parachor of the solute. The observations were carried out at the temperature of about 32°.

Parachor in Solution.

TABLE II.

Glucose in water.

x .	Density.	M_m .	Surface tension.	P_m .	P_x .
0.0	0.9967	18	70.59	52.34	...
.006582	1.0209	19.08	71.60	54.37	361.4
.007741	1.0254	19.25	72.04	54.71	359.1
.01196	1.0409	19.93	72.21	55.82	348.6
.01556	1.0547	20.52	72.91	56.82	340.6

Fructose in water.

0.004930	1.0166	18.81	71.78	53.84	359.2
.008796	1.0297	19.42	72.58	55.04	359.3
.01203	1.0424	19.95	72.73	55.91	349.1
.01428	1.0500	20.81	72.70	56.48	343.2

Sucrose in water.

x .	Dens	M_m .	Surface tension.	P_m .	P_x .
0·003629	1·0236	19·18	71·98	54·53	666·8
·006229	1·0423	19·55	72·86	54·80	666·2
·007638	1·0504	20·47	73·10	57·01	663·7
·01000	1·0684	21·24	73·41	58·24	642·2

Maltose in water.

0·002098	1·0118	18·69	71·13	53·63	667·3
·003999	1·0238	19·30	71·45	54·80	667·9
·005448	1·0340	19·77	71·96	55·68	664·5
·008640	1·0534	20·79	72·18	57·55	655·1

In Table III, the figures within parentheses are obtained from the curves given above.

TABLE III.

Glucose in pyridine.

x .	Density.	M	Surface tension.	P_m .	P_x .
0·0	0·9734	79	35·32	197·7	...
·01159	0·9830	80·17	35·72	199·5	355·4
·01536	0·9879	89·54	35·74	200·0	351·9
1·0	...	...	...	...	(860·0)

Fructose in pyridine.

0·01806	0·9889	80·82	35·91	200·8	342·6
·02507	0·9941	81·53	36·16	201·2	335·1
·03217	1·0006	82·24	36·46	202·0	329·6
·06508	1·0301	85·56	37·61	205·7	321·4
1·0	...	...	...	...	(358·0)

Sucrose in pyridine.

0·004318	0·9799	80·13	35·21	199·2	555·8
·005301	0·9809	80·38	35·63	200·2	528·3
·008160	0·9857	81·18	35·19	200·8	477·9
1·0	...	...	...	...	(664·0)

Maltose in pyridine.

x .	Density.	Surface tension.	M_m .	P_m .	P_x .
0·01020	0·9908	81·69	36·08	202·1	625·0
·01854	1·0020	83·87	36·04	205·0	593·3
·02252	1·0102	84·91	36·15	206·2	577·3
·02685	1·0175	86·06	36·24	207·4	558·8
1·0	...	...	...	...	(663·0)

SUMMARY.

The surface tension and density of glucose, fructose, sucrose and maltose were determined in the fused state as well as in solution and the parachor calculated. The parachor values were found to agree with the ring structures as proposed by Haworth and his collaborators.

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